

1 Innovative *in vivo* and *in vitro* bioassays for the establishment of toxicity thresholds of pollutants
2 in sediment quality assessment using polychaetes and their immune cells

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BIOASSAYS

Hediste diversicolor polychaete

Paracentrotus lividus sea urchin

In vivo

In vitro

Sea Urchin Embryo Test

7d

2h & 24 h

Exposure to Cu & AgNPs

48 h

Organism and tissue level endpoints

Toxicity Thresholds

	LC ₅₀	mg/L
Cu	2 h	13.4
	24 h	42
AgNPs	2 h	2.2
	24 h	0.43

21 **Abstract**

22 Sediment toxicity testing has become a crucial component for assessing the risks posed by
23 contaminated sediments and for the development of sediment quality assessment strategies.
24 Commonly used organisms for bioassays with estuarine sediments include amphipods, *Arenicola*
25 *marina* polychaetes and echinoids. Among the latter, the Sea Urchin Embryo test (SET) is the
26 most widely used. However, one relevant limitation of this bioassay is the unavailability of
27 gametes all year-round, particularly outside the natural spawning seasons. Consequently, the
28 establishment of an appropriate and complementary model organism for a continuous
29 assessment of sediment quality is recommended. A reliable assessment of the hazards resulting
30 from pollutants in sediments or pore water, can be achieved with ecologically relevant species of
31 sediment such as the polychaete *Hediste diversicolor*, which is widespread in estuaries and has
32 the capacity to accumulate pollutants. The aim of this work was to develop reliable *in vivo* and *in*
33 *vitro* bioassays with *H. diversicolor* and its coelomocytes (immune cells) to determine the toxicity
34 thresholds of different contaminants bounded to sediments or resuspended into water.
35 Polychaetes were exposed to sublethal concentrations of CuCl₂ (*in vivo*) and a non-invasive
36 method for collection of polychaetes coelomocytes was applied for the *in vitro* bioassay,
37 exposing cells to a series of CuCl₂ and AgNPs concentrations. Same reference toxicants were
38 used to expose *Paracentrotus lividus* following the SET (ICES Nº 51; Beiras et al., 2012) and
39 obtained toxicity thresholds were compared between the two species. *In vivo* exposure of
40 polychaetes to high concentrations of Cu produced weight loss and histopathological alterations.
41 After *in vitro* approaches, a significant decrease in coelomocytes viability was recorded for both
42 toxicants, in a monotonic dose-response curve, at very short-exposure times (2 h). The toxicity
43 thresholds obtained with polychaetes were in line with the ones obtained with the SET,
44 concluding that their sensitivity is similar. In conclusion, *in vivo* and *in vitro* bioassays developed
45 with *H. diversicolor* are accurate toxicity screenings of pollutants that could be bounded to
46 sediments or dissolved in the pore water, and may complement the SET outside the spawning

47 period of the echinoderms. The bioassays herein developed could be applied not only to
48 establish the toxicity thresholds of individual compounds or mixtures, but also to assess the
49 toxicity of field collected sediments.

50

51

52 **Key words:** *Hediste diversicolor*; Sediment toxicity test; biomarkers; *in vitro*; coelomocytes

53

Highlights

The bioassays with *H. diversicolor* accurately assess sediment-bounded pollutants effects

The toxicity of Cu and AgNPs were envisaged at very short-exposure times with coelomocytes

The toxic responses of *H. diversicolor* were similar to the thresholds obtained with SET

In vitro approaches with coelomocytes showed great potential for sediment ecotoxicology

54 1. Introduction

55 Estuaries have undergone important inputs of different chemicals over years due to
56 industrial exploitation and urban wastes release (Brand et al., 2018; Ruiz et al., 2020). As a
57 result, many estuarine sediments can be considered as reservoirs of persistent toxic substances
58 introduced in coastal environments by human activities, acting as a sink and source of
59 contaminants that can pose a risk for the environment (Irabien et al., 2018). A reliable
60 assessment of the hazards resulting from pollutants in sediments can be achieved after
61 integrating chemical analysis and ecotoxicological studies (Hansen et al., 2007; Chapman et al.,
62 2013, Boehler et al., 2017). Sediment toxicity tests expose organisms to sediments under
63 controlled conditions in order to give an estimation of the level of toxicity of contaminated
64 sediments in the field (Simpson et al., 2017) and have the advantage to reflect the bioavailable
65 fraction of contaminants, which can be very different from the total amount determined by
66 chemical analysis (Bat, 2005). Despite significant advances have been made in the use of
67 biological effects based toxicity indices in risk assessment (Altenburger et al., 2019; De Baat et
68 al., 2019), the consideration of the risk for benthic biota is still poorly represented in sediment
69 quality assessment strategies and improvements could be implemented. Sediment toxicity
70 testing with ecologically relevant species should become a crucial component for assessing the
71 risks posed by contaminated sediments and for the development of sediment quality
72 assessment strategies (OECD, 2007; Scrimshaw et al., 2007; De Baat et al., 2019) and dredged
73 material regulations (Hansen et al., 2007; CIEM, 2015).

74 The most commonly used benthic organisms for bioassays to assess the toxicity of marine
75 and estuarine sediments include amphipods (EPA, 1994; Casado-Martinez et al., 2006), *Arenicola*
76 *marina* polychaetes (Bat, 1998; Thain and Bifield, 2001) and echinoids (Hansen et al., 2007),
77 being each model representative of different forms of exposure (e.g. solid or liquid phase). With
78 echinoids, the sea urchin embryo test (SET) has been worldwide used as a rapid, sensitive, and
79 cost-effective biological tool for the evaluation of seawater quality (Beiras et al., 2001; Losso et

80 al., 2007; Saco-Álvarez et al., 2010). The SET has been also described for sediment toxicity
81 screenings by exposing embryos to elutriates coming from the sediment and using size increase
82 as a quantitative endpoint (Beiras et al., 2012). In addition, developmental abnormalities can be
83 measured in larvae after exposure to sediment elutriates, since a high sensitivity of
84 skeletogenesis to specific contaminants has been demonstrated (Carballeira et al., 2012). Some
85 relevant limitations of this bioassay are the unavailability of sea urchins gametes all year-round,
86 particularly outside the natural spawning seasons, at least in temperate and/or cold
87 environments, and the need of 48 h to perform the test. Consequently, the establishment of an
88 appropriate and complementary model organism for a continuous assessment of sediment
89 quality is recommended. Most of the endobenthic organisms and polychaete worms in
90 particular, are in close contact with sediments and ingest subsurface sediments that could have
91 potential toxicants bounded. Among them, the common ragworm *Hediste diversicolor*, a
92 deposit-feeder found in both sandy and muddy sediments of the European and the North
93 American coast of the Atlantic Ocean (Smith et al., 1996), tolerates a broad range of salinities
94 and temperatures in estuaries (Scaps, 2002; Ashley and Budd, 2016). They are usually available
95 throughout the year and play important roles in the food chain and consequently, in the
96 sediment community organisation (Bat, 2005). The bioturbation due to their activity is an
97 important determinant for sediment biogeochemistry and element cycling, and also for oxygen
98 availability in burrow environments that may affect growth and population sizes of the
99 associated meioorganisms (Palomo & Iribarne, 2000; Scaps, 2002). The easy sampling and
100 maintenance under laboratory conditions of ragworms (tolerance to temperature, salinity, and
101 oxygen levels), and their high degree of responsiveness (quick response to environmental
102 stressors), make *H. diversicolor* particularly suitable for ecotoxicological studies, likely to uptake
103 metals through metal-bound particles and from pore water (Ghribi et al., 2019; Silva et al.,
104 2020). Hence, several works demonstrated *H. diversicolor* to be sensitive to common
105 contaminants (Moreira et al., 2006; Bouraoui et al., 2016), but also to chemicals of emerging

106 concern in the sediment or in the water column (Cong et al., 2014; Fonseca et al., 2017; Silva et
107 al., 2020; Abouda et al., 2022). These characteristics make this a suitable species for
108 biomonitoring campaigns (Durou et al., 2007), for acute and metal accumulation pattern
109 bioassays (Burlinson et al., 2007; Cong et al., 2014) and for the application of multi-biomarker
110 approaches (Buffet et al., 2013; Catalano et al., 2012; De Marchi et al., 2017; Fonseca et al.,
111 2017; Freitas et al., 2017; Ghiribi et al., 2019). The biomarkers were mainly associated with
112 cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, changes in metabolism, lipid peroxidation and neuro and
113 genotoxicity; all involved in the toxic response to common anthropogenic chemicals. Similarly,
114 observation of histological alterations and/or damage of somatic tissues such as the digestive
115 epithelia (tissue-level biomarkers) could be expected in *H. diversicolor* under pollution
116 conditions. Detailed histological studies about the microanatomy of the digestive epithelia in
117 polychaetes are scarce (Rodrigo et al., 2015) and, moreover, histopathological alterations have
118 not been widely used as tissue-level biomarkers to assess biological effects of pollution like in
119 other marine species (i.e. mussels; Garmendia et al., 2010).

120 A variety of standardized immunoassays have been developed with soil earthworms in order to
121 assess the immunotoxic potential of toxicants based on cell-mediated and humoral responses
122 (Hayashi & Engelmann, 2013; Irizar et al., 2014, 2015; Engelmann et al., 2016; Garcia-Velasco et
123 al., 2019). Marine polychaetes possess similar immune mechanisms and cells (coelomocytes) to
124 those of earthworms which could serve for the development of adequate and sensitive
125 bioassays for toxicity screening of sediments (Cuvillier-Hot et al., 2014; Arredondo et al., 2020).
126 In fact, in previous works with *H. diversicolor* cellular endpoints have been quantified in
127 coelomocytes after *in vivo* exposure, with good results for environmental health assessment
128 (Catalano et al., 2012; Cong et al., 2014; Fonseca et al. 2017, 2019). Moreover, the use of
129 coelomocyte primary cultures would be a promising tool to determine sediment pollution
130 effects in a rapid, simple and non-invasive form, since these cells, unlike sea urchin embryos, are
131 available all along the year. The aim of this work was to develop quick, reliable and innovative *in*

132 *vivo* and *in vitro* sediment toxicity tests with ecologically relevant species such as *H. diversicolor*
133 and its coelomocytes. Two model toxicants CuCl₂ and silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were used as
134 test substances, and the results of the bioassays were compared with the toxicity thresholds
135 obtained by the standardized bioassay SET (Beiras et al., 2012) performed with species
136 recommended in regulatory guidelines, the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*. The improvement of
137 ecologically relevant bioassays could contribute to render more robust sediment toxicity
138 tests/protocols: combining multiple species to be developed all year round, varying exposure
139 pathways and including outcomes (histopathology and cytotoxicity) complementary to acute
140 endpoints (mortality, growth, behaviour).

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142 **2. Materials and methods**

143 **2.1. Test organisms**

144 *H. diversicolor* polychaetes, purchased from the commercial dealer Cebocuc® (Galicia, Spain)
145 were received in the laboratory one day after manual collections in the Galician coasts and
146 readily placed in the acclimation tanks (30 L). The latter were filled with a layer of clean
147 sediment (6 cm) collected in Plentzia (43°40'6.746'' N, 2°95'1.060'' W; Butroe estuary) and
148 seawater directly taken from the Plentzia Bay, naturally filtered by sand in the uptake wells
149 aided with a pump that sent the water to the marine station. The tanks had a constant seawater
150 flow with a salinity range of 32-33‰ and constant aeration. The acclimation laboratory had a
151 controlled temperature of 18 °C, with a photoperiodic system of 12/12 hours of artificial
152 light/darkness. Ragworms were kept in the acclimation tanks for 7 days prior to the bioassay,
153 being fed with commercial fish food (Vipagram granular, 41.9 % protein and 8.7 % fat) twice a
154 week.

155 Adult *P. lividus* were collected in a rocky shore in Armintza (43°43'3.625'' N, 2°89'9.262'' W; Bay
156 of Biscay), in April 2019. The organisms were transported alive to the laboratory and were

157 placed in aquaria with seawater at controlled temperature (16 ± 1 °C) for 2-3 weeks prior
158 experimentation. Macroalgae were given weekly as food supply until spawning induction.

159 **2.2. *In vivo* experiments with *H. diversicolor***

160 **2.2.1. *Sediment spiking procedure and characterization***

161 Test sediments were collected in the same sampling point as those used for the acclimation
162 tanks of polychaetes (Plentzia, Butroe estuary). According to previous metal characterization of
163 sediments from Plentzia collected in September 2018 (Supplementary Material-Table S1) and in
164 2019 (Table 1), and to Blanco-Rayón et al. (2019), this site showed no significant metallic
165 contamination and even showed reduced values for all the metal analysed between both years.
166 A physico-chemical characterization, including oxidable organic matter (OM) content, texture (%
167 of sand, silt and clay) and water holding capacity (WHC) was performed in CSR laboratories
168 (Jaén, Spain). In addition, pH, electrical conductivity (EC) and salinity were also determined
169 (Table 2).

170 Sediments were sampled and stored according to Thain and Bifield (2001) and King et al. (2004)
171 with some modifications (sieved at 4 mm after air drying). Part of the dried sediments were
172 artificially contaminated with copper (Cu) by spiking them with filtered seawater solutions
173 containing Cu salts ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma Aldrich, prepared in volumetric flasks, 1 M HCl-washed
174 glassware) in different quantities to obtain the desired concentrations (0, 50, 150 and 300 mg Cu
175 /kg). Copper was selected as model contaminant and because is the reference toxicant in sea
176 urchin embryo test. Copper concentrations were selected on the basis that 50 mg Cu/kg
177 represent low pollution levels (Menchaca et al., 2012), and 150 mg Cu/Kg and 300 mg Cu/kg
178 produced chronic and acute toxic effects, respectively (Férard and Blaise, 2013; Watson et al.,
179 2018). Spiked sediments were thoroughly homogenized with a clean polyethylene spatula and
180 were left to stabilize for 14 days, by mixing them every 2 days (King et al., 2004). Copper

181 concentrations were measured in spiked sediments (58, 134, 235 mg/kg) and were similar to the
182 nominal ones (50, 150, 300 mg/kg) (Table 1), indicating a proper spiking procedure and
183 stabilization period.

184 **2.2.2. Experimental set up and performance**

185 The experimental procedure was designed following the guidelines outlined by Thain and Bifield
186 (2001), with small modifications. Test tanks (5 L, polyethylene) were filled with 1 Kg of stabilized
187 sediments (resulting in 3 cm layer) and 3.75 L of seawater (0.2 µm-filtered, 30 ‰-3.5 L seawater
188 +250 mL distilled water- to obtain a final salinity of 32-33 ‰ after contact with sediment),
189 reaching 12 cm in height and obtaining a sediment-overlying water depth ratio of 1:4. All test
190 tanks were allowed to settle over a period of 24 hours.

191 *H. diversicolor* polychaetes of similar weight (3.0-3.3 g) were weighted in pools of five
192 individuals, and maintained in tanks with control (CT) and artificially polluted sediments with Cu,
193 for 7 days. Three replicates were prepared for each treatment. Continuous airflow, 18°C and
194 photoperiod (12/12h light: dark) conditions were kept during the experiment, being the physico-
195 chemical parameters of the seawater (pH, temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen-DO-)
196 monitored with a multiparametric probe (YSI Professional Plus). Ragworms were not fed during
197 the 7 days of exposure.

198 At the end of the experiment, sediment samples were collected to determine the concentration
199 of 20 metals (Li, Mo, Ag, Sn, Sb, Ba, W, Hg, Tl, Pb, Ti, Co, Zn, As, Cd, V, Cr; Mn, Ni, Se) by ICP-MS
200 (NexION 300, Perkin Elmer). Briefly, about 0.5 g of each dried and sieved sample was subjected
201 to an extraction procedure with 3.9 mL of nitric acid (69%, Tracepur, Merck), 6.2 mL of
202 hydrochloric acid (37%, Tracepur, Merck) and 9.8 mL Milli-Q quality water (Millipore, Billerica,
203 MA, USA). Ultrasound energy was applied for 6 min by means of a HD 2070 Sonopuls Ultrasonic
204 Homogenizer (Bandelin, Germany) equipped with a 6mm glass tip. The acid extract was filtered

205 using a 0.45 µm PVDF filter and diluted in Milli-Q water. Different dilutions were prepared in
206 order to match the element concentrations to the dynamic range of the instrument. In all the
207 cases the concentration of HNO₃ in the dilutions was adjusted to 1%.

208 **2.2.3. *Organisms and tissue level endpoints***

209 At the end of the experiment, polychaetes were removed from the tanks, mortality checked and
210 pools of organisms were again weighted to determine weight loss. A midgut body portion
211 (segments 20-25) of the polychaetes (n=5) was dissected out, fixed in formalin (10% commercial
212 Formaldehyde in Phosphate Buffer Saline-PBS-with 0.17 M NaCl, stored at 4 °C) and routinely
213 processed for histology (Martoja & Martoja-Pierson, 1970). Histopathological alterations were
214 addressed in transversal paraffin sections stained with Haematoxylin-Eosin, analysed under a
215 light microscope (Nikon ECLIPSE Ni). Polychaetes collected from the acclimation tank at the
216 beginning of the experiment (referred as CT0) and after 7 d in non-spiked sediments (CT7) were
217 used as reference of the anatomical and physiological states of the purchased animals. In
218 addition, metal accumulation in tissues was measured in 5 polychaetes of all treatments.

219 **2.3. *In vitro* approaches with *H. diversicolor* coelomocytes**

220 **2.3.1. *Coelomocyte extrusion and seeding in microplate***

221 Coelomocytes were extruded together with coelomic fluid following a non-invasive procedure
222 based on a previously developed method for earthworms (Irizar et al., 2014). Polychaetes were
223 kept voiding their gut contents in constant seawater flow during 24 h and were thoroughly
224 cleaned to remove any sediment particle attached to the body. Organisms were individually
225 placed in glass petri dishes and coelomocytes were extruded by electric stimulation (9 V) using
226 0.35 M NaCl PBS, with 0.02% EDTA and 1% antibiotics (Antibiotic antimycotic solution (x100):
227 10,000 units penicillin, 10 mg streptomycin and 25 µg amphotericin B per mL). Extrusion solution
228 was adjusted to the salinity of polychaetes coelomic fluid (0.17 M NaCl) taking into account the
229 dilution factor after exposure in the microplate wells. The presence of gametes in the solution

230 was checked under light microscope and only the cell solutions extruded from females
231 (containing oocytes) were collected. In order to avoid the oocytes, the coelomocyte solution was
232 filtered through a 40 µm strainer in a centrifugation step (500 rpm, 2 min). Cell solutions
233 extruded from 8-10 females were pooled together, coelomocytes were counted with the aid of a
234 Neubauer chamber and the cellular concentration adjusted to 5×10^5 cells/mL. Coelomocytes in
235 coelomic fluid based medium were then seeded in microplates (100 µL, 5×10^4 cells/well) and
236 were left stabilizing for 1h at 18 °C before exposure. For each pollutant (Cu, AgNPs) and
237 exposure time (2 and 24 h), three microplates were prepared (filled with cell solutions from
238 different pools, Supplementary Material-Fig. S1).

239 **2.3.2. Coelomocyte exposure and viability assays**

240 *H. diversicolor* coelomocyte responses *in vitro* were obtained by exposing cells to a range of
241 concentrations (0, 0.05, 1, 5, 10, 50 mg/L) of CuCl₂ and to AgNPs. AgNPs were PVP-PEI coated
242 with a size of 5.08 ± 2.03 nm, and Z-potential of 18.6 mV. Exposures were performed by addition
243 of 100 µL of exposure solution, filling eight wells per concentration. As control, 0.17 M NaCl PBS
244 was used. After 2 and 24h of exposure, coelomocyte viability (Calcein-AM) was assessed through
245 a microplate assay. The schematic diagram of the experimental design followed for the *in vitro*
246 exposure of *H. diversicolor* coelomocytes to Cu and AgNPs is illustrated in SM-Fig. S1.

247 The Calcein-AM Viability assay provides a simple, rapid, and accurate method to measure cell
248 viability and cytotoxicity. The calcein acetoxymethyl ester (Calcein AM) permeates live cells and
249 is hydrolyzed by intracellular esterase to calcein, a hydrophilic and strongly fluorescent
250 compound that is well retained in the cell cytoplasm (Bratosin et al., 2005). The Calcein-AM
251 viability test was performed according to Garcia-Velasco et al. (2019), with slight modifications
252 (removal of washing steps). In half of the plates wells, 2 µl of Calcein-AM Working solution (2.5
253 µM Calcein/well) were added. In the remaining wells, 2 µl of PBS were added in order to
254 overcome background noise (SM-Fig. S1). After 40 min of incubation (18 °C, darkness),

255 fluorescence was read at 490/20 nm excitation, and 520/20 nm emission in Cytation 3 Cell
256 Imaging multi-mode reader (BioTek Inc.). Supposing that the control group has the maximum
257 calcein retention capacity (100%), the relative values were calculated. In addition, the median
258 lethal concentration (LC₅₀) was calculated.

259 **2.4. Sea Urchin Embryo Test (SET): reference bioassay in sediment toxicology**

260 In parallel, the SET (Beiras et al., 2012) was performed, exposing fertilized eggs of *P. lividus*, to
261 the same reference toxicants at a range of exposure concentrations (CuCl₂: 0, 0.005, 0.05, 0.5, 5
262 mg Cu/L; AgNPs: 0, 0.005, 0.05, 0.5, 5, 50 mg /L). After 48h, embryo size increase and
263 developmental abnormalities were measured. Size increase consisted on the measurements of
264 the maximum dimension of 50 embryos per vial, while malformations were recorded on 100
265 embryos/vial following Carballeira et al. (2012). A general index of toxicity (IT), that weight the
266 degree of developmental abnormalities by the frequency, was then calculated for each
267 treatment. With size increase results, the median effect concentration (EC₅₀) was calculated for
268 each toxicant.

269 **2.5. Statistical analysis**

270 The statistical analysis of the data was carried out with the aid of the SPSS statistical package
271 (IMB SPSS Statistics 23). Shapiro-Wilk (n<30) and Levene's tests were performed to study
272 normality and equality of variances of the datasets, respectively. Datasets were analysed with
273 Kruskal-Wallis followed by Dunn's post-hoc test and significant differences were established at
274 $p < 0.05$. In order to estimate the median lethal and effect concentration (LC₅₀, EC₅₀) the Probit
275 model was used.

276 **3. Results**

277 **3.1. *In vivo* experiments with *H. diversicolor***

278 **3.1.1. Sediment characterization**

279 The sediments collected in Plentzia and used for the *in vivo* exposure of polychaetes were
280 classified as a loamy to sand matrix (USDA, 1999), presenting 3.07 % organic matter and a water
281 holding capacity of 22.3% (Table 2). The concentrations of metals measured in these sediments
282 (Table 1) were low and similar to those measured previously in sediments collected in
283 September 2018 (SM-Table S1), reinforcing this site as a clean site for metallic contamination
284 (Legorburu et al., 2013; Blanco-Rayón et al., 2019). Concerning the sediments from Plentzia
285 spiked with Cu, the real exposure concentrations were linearly correlated with the nominal ones.
286 Hence, at the end of the exposure a nominal concentration of 50 mg Cu/kg resulted in 58 mg/kg,
287 150 mg Cu/kg in 134 mg/kg and 300 mg Cu/kg resulted in 236 mg/kg (Table 1).

288 **3.1.2. Organism level effects**

289 *In vivo* exposure of *H. diversicolor* to Cu caused increased mortality (around 30%) after exposure
290 to 150 mg Cu/Kg, and a significant dose-response weight loss compared with the control group,
291 with a maximum (>30%) for the highest dose (300 mg Cu/Kg, Fig. 1).

292 Net metal accumulation did not occur in control polychaetes (CT7) maintained in sediments of
293 Plentzia compared with CT0. In spiked sediments, *H. diversicolor* accumulated mainly Cu, Cd and
294 Ag in tissues (Fig. 2). The concentration of Cu measured in the organisms maintained in 50 mg
295 Cu/Kg treatment were similar ($p > 0.05$) to CT0 values ($14.94 \pm 3.90 \mu\text{g/g}$ and $8.25 \pm 1.42 \mu\text{g/g}$,
296 respectively). After exposure to 150 and 300 mg Cu/kg, higher Cu concentrations were
297 measured, $48.65 \mu\text{g/g}$ and $51 \pm 8 \mu\text{g/g}$, respectively (Fig. 2 A). Enrichments of Cd and Sn occurred
298 in ragworms maintained in the highest concentration of Cu (Fig. 2 B and D), while highest Ag
299 accumulations were recorded in 50 and 300 mg Cu/Kg treatments (Fig. 2 C)

300 **3.1.3. Effects at tissue-level**

301 Control polychaetes (CT7) exhibited a normal body wall structure (tegument, epidermis) and
302 digestive epithelium integrity after 7 days of experiment (Fig. 3A). Exposure to the highest Cu
303 concentrations (150 and 300 mg Cu/Kg) showed clear blood accumulation in the intestinal areas
304 when compared to CT0 and control (CT7) polychaetes (Fig. 3). In the case of polychaetes
305 exposed to 300 mg Cu/Kg, conspicuous brown deposits were clearly observed in digestive
306 epithelia (Fig. 3D). Parasites (spores of a Mesomycetozoea parasite, unicellular amoeba-like
307 protists; Fig. 3D) were observed in the digestive epithelium of ragworms irrespective of
308 treatments. The infection with parasites does not seem to be serious for the animals since no
309 inflammation signs were recorded.

310 **3.2. *In vitro* approaches with *H. diversicolor* coelomocytes**

311 The Calcein-AM viability assay performed in coelomocytes extruded from *H. diversicolor* and
312 exposed to CuCl₂ and AgNPs showed a significant dose-response decrease in calcein retention
313 (Fig. 4). Cells exposed to longer time (24 h) showed less retention capacity than after 2 hours of
314 exposure to Cu and AgNPs (Fig. 4). Coelomocytes viability significantly decreased from 5 and 0.5
315 mg/L onwards for Cu (Fig. 4A) and AgNPs (Fig. 4B), respectively. The calculated LC₅₀ values after
316 Cu exposure were 13.4 (2 h) and 4.2 mg/L (24 h), and for AgNPs 2.2 (2 h) and 0.43 mg/L (24 h).

317 **3.3. Sea Urchin Embryo Test (SET)**

318 The SET showed that the exposure to CuCl₂ caused decrease in embryo size, being significant
319 after exposure to 5 mg Cu/L (Fig. 5A). After exposure to AgNPs, embryos showed more marked
320 effects at lower concentrations, with a significant decrease in size starting at 0.05 mg/L (Fig. 5B).
321 The EC₅₀ values for size impairments were established at 0.38 mg/L and 0.086 mg/L for Cu and
322 AgNPs, respectively. The values of the Index of toxicity (IT), were higher after exposure to the
323 highest concentrations of Cu (5 mg Cu/Kg) and from 0.5 onwards in the case of exposure to
324 AgNPs (Figs. 5C, D).

325 **Discussion**

326 In the last 15 years an exponential growth in the understanding of contaminants in estuarine
327 sediments has occurred. Accordingly, sediment quality guidelines (SQG) have recently been
328 introduced in different countries and regions although the application of these guidelines is not
329 based on a scientific consensus. SQG can be understood as trigger values or threshold
330 concentrations (Chapman & Anderson, 2005). Below this threshold the possibility to produce
331 deleterious biological effects is very low. Moreover, Chapman and Anderson (2005) suggested
332 that investigations should combine sediment chemistry (including contaminant bioavailability
333 and bioaccumulation), benthic ecology and toxicity testing. All this information will offer a rapid
334 and accurate tool in order to perform a proper management of polluted sediments.

335 The world-wide used SET test provides a general view of the toxicity exerted by chemicals
336 bioavailable in seawater by quantifying (in terms of pluteus larvae size) the degree of
337 developmental completion achieved by the embryos (Beiras et al., 2012). This bioassay endpoint
338 is a quantitative, observer-independent, automatically readable response, and have been
339 standardized and amended under several international guidelines and directives (ASTM, 1990;
340 USEPA, 1995; Environment Canada, 1997; CETESB, 1999; ASTM, 2002). Presently, SET was highly
341 sensitive to determine the toxicity thresholds for CuCl_2 and AgNPs after 48 h of exposure. In the
342 case of Cu exposure, the EC_{50} (for the size increase endpoint) was estimated in 0.38 mg/L. This
343 value is very similar to the normalized SQGs calculated for the Basque coast using three toxicity
344 tests including SET, AMBI and Microtox that was 0.55 mg Cu/L (Menchaca et al., 2012). In the
345 same line, Chapman (1999) and Choueri et al. (2009) proposed that SQG should be used in the
346 region where they were developed to better predict the toxicity of contaminants for each
347 specific coastal environment. The coincidence of this calculation suggest that this value is the
348 reference threshold for Cu in the Basque Coast. The case of AgNPs is not so clear due to the lack
349 of works regarding toxicity thresholds calculated on the basis of toxicity tests. Presently, the EC_{50}
350 for AgNPs was estimated in 0.086 mg/L, much lower that for CuCl_2 , suggesting that the SQGs

351 should be more restrictive for this contaminant. In conclusion, the sensitivity of early
352 developmental stages of sea urchin allows to evaluate the potential effects of Cu and AgNPs that
353 may potentially become available to the water column (or release to the water column due to
354 sediment resuspension) and to establish toxicity thresholds for both pollutants.

355 One of weaknesses, when planning toxicity testing with sea urchins in the framework of
356 biomonitoring programs, is the lack of continuous availability of suitable biological material
357 (gametes) outside the natural spawning season of the species. Therefore, the development of
358 bioassays with species that could complement the SET in seasons outside the spawning period
359 would be very welcome. One recommendation is the use of epi-/benthic test species (ECHA
360 2014), which are in direct contact with the sediment and pore water, with a broad geographical
361 distribution, compatible with selected exposure methods and endpoints and have a toxicological
362 database demonstrating sensitivity to a range of contaminants (Simpson et al., 2005).
363 Endobenthic aquatic polychaetes such as *H. diversicolor* fulfil above mentioned requirements.
364 Hence, *in vivo* and *in vitro* assays have been developed with polychaetes exposed to reference
365 toxicants (CuCl₂, AgNPs), being the suitability of the assays validated through comparison with
366 the SET reference bioassay (Beiras et al., 2012).

367 After the *in vivo* bioassay, in which *H. diversicolor* were exposed during 7 d to loamy
368 sediments spiked with different Cu concentrations, they accumulated Cu in tissues following a
369 dose-dependent pattern. The massive accumulation was related with mortality rates in 150
370 mg/Kg exposure and weight losses recorded for doses ranging 150-300 mg Cu/Kg, suggesting the
371 onset of acute toxicity responses. Weight losses have been previously related with induced
372 dehydration of specimens as a result of enhanced mucus generation and excretion (exocytosis)
373 from the tegument to form a protective layer over its surface under stress conditions (Berthet et
374 al., 2003; Murray et al., 2012). Conversely, lower Cu concentrations (50 mg Cu/Kg) did not
375 produce any effect (mortality or weight loss). In contrast, exposure of other polychaete species
376 such as *A. marina* to doses slightly higher than 14 mg Cu/Kg induced lethality (LC₅₀= 20 mg/Kg;

377 Bat & Raffaelli, 1998). Moreover, Cu spiked in the water column induced mortality in *Nereis* at
378 concentrations higher than 2.3 mg Cu/L (Bryan, 1976). This might suggest different sensitivity of
379 polychaetes to pollutant insult depending on their feeding habits (microphagic feeders-
380 *Arenicola*- vs. predators –*Nereis*-), or the phase in which the pollutant is spiked (sediment vs.
381 water column).

382 Under some specific conditions competitive displacement reactions occurred after the
383 addition of metals, such as Cu and Cd in estuarine sediments (Simpson et al., 2000).
384 Interestingly, Cu exposure (300 mg Cu/kg) produced a concomitant increase in Cd and Sn levels
385 although the levels reached were very low. Simpson et al. (2000) suggested that in the Cu-spiked
386 sediments, Cd (present in the original sediment) was displaced into the pore waters becoming
387 more available for polychaetes. However, it cannot be discarded that the burrowing or
388 bioturbation activity of polychaetes can increase the release of contaminants in sediments to
389 the water column (Scaps, 2002; Martinez-Garcia, 2015). The extent to which metal additions
390 affect sediment pH and redox conditions, and disrupt the equilibrium partitioning of sediment
391 constituents, is poorly understood and deserves further investigation (Luoma & Bryan, 1982;
392 Simpson et al., 2000).

393 Assessment of the histopathological alterations produced in target organs of
394 polychaetes after exposure to pollutants has been previously reported although the amount of
395 research in this field is still very low (Geracitano et al., 2004; Murray et al., 2012). Anatomically
396 the polychaete possess a large central digestive epithelium surrounded by the coelom cavity
397 filled with gametes and coelomocytes, the nerve cord, the dorsal and ventral vessels (Rodrigo et
398 al., 2015). After exposure to Cu (high dose), an increased blood irrigation close to the digestive
399 tract and massive accumulation of brown deposits (probably lipofuscin granules) were observed
400 in digestive epithelia. These deposits are membrane-bound structures that can contain by-
401 products of the digestive process that are released to the lumen of digestive tract at more
402 advanced stages of digestion (Costa et al., 2014). Histochemical examinations of *H. diversicolor*

403 after exposure to acetylsalicylic acid have shown important increase of mucous cells in the
404 tegument (Gomes et al., 2019), but up to now, these kind of histopathological alterations have
405 not been recorded in the digestive system of polychaetes. These alterations may indicate that
406 changes at tissue level might occur under environmental stress situations and deserves more
407 attention for future sediment toxicological works.

408 The presence of parasites is indicative of a depressed immunological system due to a
409 variety of environmental factors including pollutants in aquatic animals (Benito et al., 2019).
410 Parasites were observed, mainly in the digestive epithelium of the gut, although they were
411 present in the majority of individuals regardless the treatment. There is a lack of literature on
412 polychaetes parasites, however, according to their size, general aspect (unicellular amoeba-like
413 protists) and smooth capsule, the parasites found in polychaetes seem like the active spores of a
414 Mesomycetozoa, according to Dr. Pedro Costa (Nova Univ. Lisbon, pers. comm).

415 The use of primary cultures of immune cells of invertebrates to investigate the impact of
416 pollutants in the environment have been recently outlined with promising results. In fact,
417 annelids (oligo and polychaetes) have developed cellular immunity (phagocytosis, encapsulation
418 against parasites) and possess humoral components of immunity which are essentially
419 represented by antibacterial proteins (Dhainaut & Scaps 2001; Catalano et al., 2012; Hayashi &
420 Engelmann, 2013; Cong et al., 2014; Cuvillier-Hot et al., 2014; Irizar et al., 2015; García-Velasco
421 et al., 2019). Presently, *in vitro* approaches were optimized for marine worms (polychaetes *H.*
422 *diversicolor*) based on a previously developed method for earthworms (Irizar et al., 2014). The
423 modifications in the protocol included the use of coelomic based medium (with PBS adjusted to
424 polychaetes coelom osmolarity) to maintain the cells in culture, the shortening of the exposure
425 to 2 and 24 hours (avoiding medium replacements) and the removal of washing steps when
426 performing the Calcein-AM viability test. *In vitro* exposure of coelomocytes to a series of Cu
427 concentrations produced a significant dose-response decrease in the viability of cells. Likely,
428 chronic copper exposure impaired the immunological response of the polychaete *Eurythoe*

429 *complanata* with changes in coelomocytes viability, number and phagocytosis capacity (Nusetti
430 et al., 1998). Exposure to AgNPs exerted more toxic effects than Cu according to LC₅₀ values after
431 2 and 24 h. Similarly, exposure to AgNPs caused cytotoxicity in coelomocytes of *Eisenia fetida*
432 being EC₅₀ 6 mg AgNP/L (García-Velasco et al., 2019). Additionally, these authors found a
433 selective toxicity in amoebocytes more than in eleocytes (subpopulations of coelomocytes), that
434 was the opposite for non-particulated contaminants (ionic Cu) in which the target were the
435 eleocytes (Irizar et al., 2015). More work is needed to assess the differential role in metal
436 handling regarding the two subpopulation of coelomocytes in polychaetes, although it can be
437 concluded the capacity of the test to predict impairments caused by pollutants (toxicity
438 thresholds) and provide rapid and valuable information for (cyto)toxicology.

439 The sensitivity of this innovative *in vitro* bioassay based in coelomocyte viability
440 reflected the same response pattern obtained using the SET with similar sensitivity. That is, Cu
441 exposure exerted a significant toxicity effect on cell viability already after exposure to 10 mg
442 Cu/L, while SET showed toxicity between 5-10 mg Cu/L. The response of coelomocytes could be
443 envisaged after 2 h (with similar results after 24 h) while SET was showing toxicity after the 48 h
444 of duration of the test. The results obtained after exposure to AgNPs were similar but with more
445 power of discrimination for SET vs. coelomocyte culturing: 0.5 mg AgNP/L vs. 1-5 mg AgNP/L,
446 respectively. Maybe, dissimilar dissolution rates of AgNPs in seawater media and coelomic fluid
447 based culture media (10 ‰ salinity) could be responsible of this slight discrepancy between
448 methods. Nevertheless, the values of the IT, calculated from the frequency of malformations
449 detected in exposed sea urchin embryos, were in line with the responses obtained for
450 coelomocytes. Hence, it can be concluded that the sensitivity of the size endpoint in SET is
451 slightly higher although coelomocyte bioassay showed faster responses that can be used for a
452 quick screening of toxicity. Furthermore, primary cultures of coelomocytes may render high-
453 throughput amount of data in a short time when cells are seeded and exposed in wells and read
454 in a microplate. Finally, it is suggested that this toxicity screening could be applied not only to

455 establish the toxicity thresholds of individual compounds or mixtures, but also to assess the
456 toxicity of elutriates coming from field collected sediments.

457 **4. Conclusions**

458 The bioassays developed with *Hediste diversicolor* (*in vivo*) and their coelomocytes (*in vitro*) are
459 useful tools to assess the effects of pollutants that can be bounded to sediments or resuspended
460 into water. The toxicity thresholds obtained with both assays were in line with the ones
461 obtained with the sea urchin embryo test (SET), concluding that their sensitivity is similar. The
462 optimization of the methodology for primary cultures of *H. diversicolor* coelomocytes (non-
463 invasive extrusion method, use of coelomic fluid based medium, viability assay with removal of
464 washing steps) can be of great importance for sediment toxicity assessment since it allows
465 performing rapid and simultaneous screening of toxicants (including individual compounds or
466 mixtures and elutriates of real sediments). *In vivo* and *in vitro* bioassays with polychaetes and
467 their coelomocytes may be cost-effective tools for toxicity screening and may complement the
468 SET outside the spawning period of the echinoderms when gametes are not available to perform
469 the test.

470

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709 Table 1. Metal characterization of sediments collected in Plentzia, showing metal
 710 concentrations of 20 elements in control and artificially polluted sediments with three CuCl₂
 711 concentrations (50, 150 and 300 mg Cu/Kg).

Metal characterization (mg/Kg)	Control (Plentzia)	50 mg Cu/Kg	150 mg Cu/Kg	300 mg Cu/Kg
Cu	25.87 ± 3.07	57.77 ± 3.33	134.25 ± 5.88	235.93 ± 16.76
Li	16.00 ± 0.12	15.76 ± 0.72	16.87 ± 1.57	15.51 ± 2.7
Mo	1.28 ± 0.37	0.85 ± 0.04	1.60 ± 0.86	0.85 ± 0.22
Ag	0.18 ± 0.03	0.16 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.02
Sn	4.28 ± 0.94	4.46 ± 0.95	4.06 ± 0.13	4.33 ± 3.53
Sb	0.36 ± 0.04	0.20 ± 0.12	0.40 ± 0.09	0.41 ± 0.04
Ba	83.2 ± 3.87	89.15 ± 8.41	94.24 ± 8.51	80.88 ± 6.57
W	0.25 ± 0.00	0.20 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.15	0.25 ± 0.18
Hg	0.46 ± 0.15	0.38 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.06	0.42 ± 0.05
Tl	0.17 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02
Pb	29.90 ± 1.95	28.68 ± 0.77	30.01 ± 4.94	29.93 ± 0.80
Ti	104.12 ± 1.74	109.54 ± 8.20	116.20 ± 16.03	119.75 ± 7.69
Co	5.55 ± 1.74	6.37 ± 1.64	5.83 ± 0.33	5.74 ± 0.34
Zn	138.33 ± 9.52	134.77 ± 6.32	146.35 ± 6.2	142.77 ± 2.21
As	13.83 ± 0.44	16.45 ± 2.76	17.36 ± 0.07	14.35 ± 0.88
Cd	0.32 ± 0.10	0.41 ± 0.19	0.32 ± 0.09	0.35 ± 0.07
V	20.61 ± 0.28	20.72 ± 0.71	22.33 ± 0.90	20.23 ± 2.12
Cr	12.7 ± 0.21	12.89 ± 0.47	13.91 ± 0.65	12.78 ± 1.11
Ni	9.29 ± 0.11	10.43 ± 2.00	9.76 ± 0.47	9.54 ± 0.31
Se	0.62 ± 0.09	0.88 ± 0.10	0.89 ± 0.11	0.76 ± 0.08

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714 Table 2. Physico-chemical characterization (oxidizable organic matter in %p/p, texture as % of
 715 sand, silt and clay, Water Holding Capacity-WHC in %p/p, pH, electrical conductivity in mS/cm
 716 and salinity in g NaCl/L) of the sediment used for experimentation.

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SEDIMENT SITE	SAMPLING DATA	OXIDIZABLE O.M (%p/p)	TEXTURE				WHC (%p/p)	pH	EC (mS/cm)	SALINITY (g/L)
			Sand	Silt	Clay	USDA Soil Class.				
Plentzia	Sept 2018	3.07	53	35	12	Loamy-Sand	22.3	7.59	15.79	8.83

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723 Fig. 1. Mortality and weight loss (in %) of *H. diversicolor* after *in vivo* exposure to control and Cu
 724 spiked (50, 150 and 300 mg/Kg) sediments. Values are represented as average \pm standard
 725 deviations and significant differences ($p < 0.05$ with Kruskal-Wallis) between treatments are
 726 represented by asterisk.

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737 Fig.2. Metal accumulation (Cu, Cd, Ag, Sn) in tissues of *H. diversicolor* after 7 d *in vivo* exposure
 738 to CuCl₂ (50, 150 and 300 mg Cu/Kg) spiked in the sediments. Values are represented as average
 739 \pm standard deviations.

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743 Fig. 3. Digestive tract in transversal sections of *H. diversicolor* at the beginning of the experiment
 744 (t0) (A), after 7 days in control sediment (B), and after 7 d exposure to 150 mg Cu/Kg (C) and 300
 745 mg Cu/Kg (D). Blood irrigation is labelled with an asterisk (*) and brown deposits with an arrow.
 746 Epithelium (E), Oocytes (Oo), Parasites (P). Scale bar: 100 µm.

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756 Fig. 4. Cell viability (Calcein AM viability assay, represented by calcein retention in % relative to
 757 the control) in primary cultures of *H. diversicolor* coelomocytes exposed to CuCl₂ (A) and AgNPs
 758 (B) (n=3). Values are represented as means ± standard deviations and the significant differences
 759 (p≤0.05 with Kruskal-Wallis) are represented by letters (a,b,c for 2 h and A,B,C for 24 h).

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763 Fig. 5. Size increase (% to control; A, B) and the index of toxicity (IT; C, D) calculated from the
 764 frequency of malformations detected in embryos exposed to Cu (A, C) and AgNPs (B, D)..
 765 Significant differences (p≤0.05 with Kruskal-Wallis) are represented by letters (a,b,c).

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767 SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

768 Table S1. Initial metal characterization of the sediments collected in Plentzia in September 2018.

SEDIMENT METAL CHARACTERIZATION (mg/Kg)	Cu	Li	Mo	Ag	Sn	Sb	Ba	W	Hg	Tl
		32.34 ± 3.92	21.07 ± 0.12	1.52 ± 0.18	0.17 ± 0.01	5.35 ± 0.44	0.82 ± 0.06	111.62 ± 15.15	0.19 ± 0.03	0.53 ± 0.04
	Pb	Ti	Co	Zn	As	Cd	V	Cr	Ni	Se
	42.59 ± 5.24	345.59 ± 25.84	16.31 ± 0.86	243.45 ± 32.32	19.32 ± 3.00	0.36 ± 0.00	57.02 ± 1.99	38.29 ± 3.64	24.83 ± 2.38	3.67 ± 0.23

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772 Fig. S1. Schematic diagram of the experimental design followed for the *in vitro* exposure of *H.*

773 *diversicolor* coelomocytes to Cu and AgNPs (0, 0.05, 1, 5, 10, 50 mg/L) for 2 and 24 hours. Green

774 colored wells in the microplate indicated the addition of Calcein-AM for the coelomocyte

775 viability assay.

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Author Contributions Statement

Garcia-Velasco, Nerea: Investigation (samplings, in vivo and in vitro experiment design and development), Methodology (optimization of in vitro method with coelomocytes), Data acquisition and curation (graphs, tables and statistics), Writing (original draft, reviews and editing).

Carrero, Jose Antonio: Investigation (chemical sample processing and analysis), Methodology, Data curation (tables), Writing (review and editing).

Urionabarrenetxea, Erik: Investigation (samplings, support for in vitro experiment), Methodology (support in the optimization of in vitro method with coelomocytes), Writing (review).

Doni, Lucia: Investigation (samplings, support for in vivo experiment), Writing (support for the original draft)

Zaldibar, Beñat: Data curation, Supervision, Writing (review and editing)

Izagirre, Urtzi: Investigation (breeding of laboratory animals, experimental design in aquaria), Data curation, Supervision, Writing (review and editing)

Soto, Manu: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Data curation, Writing (original draft, reviews and editing).